

A Global Change in Education through Information Technology and Communication

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ABSTRACT

The present paper explain that how information communication and technology brought revolutionary change in global industrial, economic, social and cultural aspect of every society in globe. It has the ability to enhance every type of development in the society. Education is the only means to incorporate information & communication technology is the development aspect of society. This paper shows the speed by which the Government and specifically education bureau crucial can formulate policies plan forward or simply react are put to the test. The change in education is according to need of change. It needs a changed and pragmatist mind set among teachers and policy makers.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization has ushered in an era of one world market in which the education, economy and welfare can be gauged to assess its efficiencies and role of governance. Since the trends towards globalization are changing the world's preconceived notions about social modernization, channels of communication, promotion of globalization etc. explore how nations epitomizing neither effective role play. The education sector over the years has become sizable and is a growing business across the globe. The world has entered into an information and communication age. Developments in information and communication technology is going to open up new and cost effective approaches for expanding the reach of education to children, youths as well as to those who need continuing education to meet the demands of explosion of information, fast changing nature of occupations and life long education. The consensus of opinion among social scientists and business planners is that information and communication technology is a growing area in the foreseeable future and can create vast opportunities in almost all areas of life.

The information technology and communication technology has every country on the globe. It is estimated that the contribution of knowledge and communication technology will double the global GDP in next ten years and would account for two third of the growth in global GDP. *Information and communication technology brought revolutionary change in the global industrial, economic, educational, social and cultural aspects of every society in the globe (Wanson and Narula, 1990).* New communication technologies linked the people of the world as never before. Once again, development communication policy and strategy was bound to be changed o reap the benefit of new digital communications media systems in the third world countries in the future (Guarantee 2001). Given all these

developments there is every reason to expect a period of major changes in development communication strategy in the future. Thus, from the very beginning, information and communications have played a central role at every stage of human development: agrarian, industrial, nuclear, information and globalization. To have pace with the same exploration, it is need of the hour to make the media as means rather than ends. *The preceding perspective will deal its development through the ages give a milestone for its future endeavour (Mowlana and Wislon, 1990; Combridge, 2002).*

A FUTURE EDGE IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

Information Technology is the collective term for various technologies involved in processing and transmitted information. It includes computing, telecommunications and microelectronics. Information technology has not only enabled us to work quickly but also has given decisions makers the opportunity of considering more data for making decisions. Comprehensively IT can be defined as the use of hardware and software for efficient management of information i.e. storage, retrieval processing, communication, diffusion and sharing of information. Information technology is the modern science of gathering, storing, manipulating processing and communicating desired types of information in a specific environment. "Computer Technology" and "Communication Technology" are the impact of these two in the information storage and dissemination of information centers in the educational, cultural, agricultural, scientific and technical disciplines of the world. Information needs are increasing day by day and today every person is intending to be information oriented.

Information technology has geared up by the advent of major efficient and effective technological innovations. Introduction of information technology has influenced very significantly work culture in our offices, schools, colleges etc. Information people are highly respected. The current developments and advancements in the information technology have also brought the offices to homes as their places. Almost all types of organization are going to change beyond their expectation. Information has also strengthened us in taking decisions in a more scientific way. Thus very fast technological change will definitely accelerate development in all direction.

Keeping in view the growth of IT on the our hand and the development in reaching, bearing and research on the other hand all concerned with education today are attempting to grasp how IT could help in modernizing teaching, research and learning, as without the timely assimilation of the advance of technology in the field of education, we could be left far behind in the development rave, so we need to survey the impact of IT on population education & its components, viz, the teaching, the faculty and researchers, learning, activity of research and academic libraries. The school, colleges & universities of education do not have adequate IT facilities. There is a wide Gap between IT and education.

1981	18% of USA Public School had one computer for instructional use
1983	Estimate increased to 98%
1990	Students to computer ratio in USA was 125:1
1991	Ratio was 20:1
1995	Ratio was 9:1

Through information technology is mature enough; it has to go a long way. New dimension to information technology is expected in the coming days. A few of the areas making it possible are area

of audio and video including digital optical systems. These systems are heavily desired in much application. The area of image processing is the thrust area for computer researches which has certainly satisfied the world with such gifts from time to time. This development is also expected to improve and manage different aspects of population education. By employing new information technology it will help in horizontal and cross sectional growth of children both in acquisition of knowledge and development of group learning skills. The following are the some developments expected in the future edge:

- It will enable the storing and manipulations of a large amount of data i.e. teaching with information & communication technology.
- For archival storage of documents, microfilm systems will be replaced by document image processing and digital optical storage.
- It will improve performance with an already acquired knowledge. It encompasses activities ranging from tutoring to stimulations of entire system.
- It will enable learner to construct knowledge through the use of the technology as a thinking partner, i.e. software tools in education, educational programming environments and developing educational software.

DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY

Communication development is concerned with the acquisition, establishment and control of mass media outlets by a government for deliberate employment to promote, support and sustain planned social over the last three decades, questions about development communication – its origins, trajectories and transformations have become more and more central to debates in social, economic, cultural and technology led development theory as major scholars have placed them at the heart of their past and recent work.

Communication technology brought revolutionary change in the global industrial, economic, educational, social and cultural aspects of every society in the globe. New communication technologies linked the people of the world as never before. Once again, development communication policy and strategy was bound to be changed to reap the benefit of the new digital communications media systems in the third world countries in the future (Gunaratine, 2001). Media fusion is the dense interpretation of different media like TV, radio, fax, phone, computer, word processor, electronic network, satellites or other interlinked technologies that transform the individual media into a system. Combined with globalization, it reduces the clout of any single medium, channel, and publication etc. but it endows the media system as a whole with our enormous enhanced power that permeates the planet.

We all are living in the age of media crowd. Different media are rushing to our homes and institutions, but we are not sure about the use of our appropriate media. We access to a huge number of TV Channels, but without a proper decision, there is a clash in the family about the selection of specific channel at specific time. Similar thing is also happening in our education institutions. We are getting different media for the educational purpose, but it is either misutilized for under utilized. The cause is that we do not have a proper media culture to synchronize different media to get more and more utilized. It is the time to prepare teachers to create a proper media culture among students. However, in view of the societal, concerns and to meet the demands of 21st century, the goal of education, techniques of teaching & teacher's role will have to be radically transformed.

Moreover, before starting formal schooling, most of the Indian children, will probably study in their

homes by using new information technology; integrated television, communication, information retrieval, computer, multichannel TV network, electronic games etc. due to increasing use of software and media education, self learning will assume a preeminent place. Microcomputers will be widely used for teaching basic arithmetical calculations. Word processors and video terminals may be used in the classroom for creative writing. By employing new information technology, it will help in horizontal and cross sectional growth of children both in acquisition of knowledge and development of group learning skills.

ICT BASED SOCIETY AND EDUCATION SYSTEM

Changing Technology is a part of the rapidly changing social, cultural, political and economic times in which we live. Both administrators and teachers in schools, however, are ill equipped to deal with the enormity and complexity of the technological change & going on around us. In relative terms, our programme of study and schools at sites of learning are largely low tech learning contexts in a high-tech world. If this does not change, there will rapidly become redundant. The pressure to examine the new technologies and to see how they square against the existing curricula is placing stress on the educational bureaucracy.

While talking of introducing computers and information technology in schools, there is also a pressure for basic educational amenities such as classroom which are wanting in rural and tribal schools. It is also a matter of concern. There is need to make a balance between these two. In this crucial how we cannot ignore one at the lost of other. We have to make a synchronized progress. Distance education system has overcome the handicap inherent to the conventional education system which limits its reach for those living in rural and remote areas. Technological expansion has helped the spread of education for all, irrespective of age, sex, creed, religion and socioeconomic status, who are in need of education whenever located. The emergence of the IT including the multimedia and satellite based telecommunication system has generated potential or a sea change in Education. Apart from print, radio, TV, audio-video cassettes, tape recorders, IT has led to the development of various electronic based innovations in the field of higher education which permit vision, sound & data with interactivity.

There is no denying of the fact that electric based technologies will dominate the educational scenario in the future. But if the process are not good and chorus our poor services then IT implementation will also add to the process of poor quality services. There is an urgent need to reengineer the process as such. Only employees of the department and not any IT professional can understand these processes in the true sense while India needs the fruits of IT to reach out to the citizens, it must create its appropriate technology, their local language and affordability to build up an adequate technological infrastructure to support the kind of learning needed in future.

CONCLUSION

There is a need to change in each and every sphere of society according to the time of information and communication technology. It has the ability to enhance every type of development in the society. Education is the only means to incorporate information and communication technology in the development aspects of the society.

Information and communication technology can also be used as a tool to improve the quality of education for preparing the society and its manpower to face the challenge of future. A characteristic of ICT is its phenomenal rate of growth, in magnitude as well as complexity. Rates of obsolescence are also high. As information and communication technologies get more sophisticated, so do educa-

tional technologies that are essentially the applications of information and communication technologies in the classrooms. Consequently, the speed by which the Government and specifically education bureau curacies can formulate policies, plan forward or even simply react are put to the rest. The change in education should be according to the need of the change. It needs a changed and pragmatist mind set among the teachers and policy makers.

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